

CiRLab – Coimbra Region

Report - First General Assembly

Coimbra, 5th December 2024

Credits

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13

In Brief

Cities concentrate countless socio-economic activities and are responsible for the consumption of around 70 per cent of global resources, the emission of 60-80 per cent of greenhouse gases (GHG), as well as the waste of resources, energy and water. Although this is a huge challenge, it is also an opportunity.

Urban metabolism models, such as the UMAN Model, can help define good circular economy practices, making it possible to reduce waste and reduce the environmental impacts caused by human activity.

The ECLECTIC project takes the circular economy from theory to action in cities, improving the understanding of cities as complex multi-level ecosystems with inputs, outputs and resource flows. The project aims to design, implement and monitor strategic action plans for the circular economy in cities, considering the needs of vulnerable groups and reduce inequality in the selection of circular models that benefit them.

To achieve this, the involvement of the different actors ('Stakeholders') and communities plays a crucial role in planning and implementing the appropriate actions and measures for each city/region. Living Labs for the Circular Economy in the Region/City (CiRLab - City/Region Living Lab) will therefore be set up.

By attending specific workshops, stakeholders will identify needs, strengths and solutions, foreseeing an impact on the design of a CiRLab Action Plan for the Circular Economy in the region.

In the specific case of Coimbra region CiRLab , in the first workshop, 22 stakeholders had the opportunity to explore the different conceptions of the Circular Economy, to identify the priority sectors in this area, to reflect on the role of the different regional players, as well as to list the main needs and challenges for implementing the Circular Economy in the region. The engagement process was conducted using the World Café method,

In this report, the main contributions, opinions and perceptions are presented by theme.

The workshop began with a brief presentation of the results of the UMAN Model for the Centro region, followed by a World Café, with the aim of identifying the needs and challenges in developing the Circular Economy in the city/region, with the following themes:

1. What is Circular Economy?
2. What are the priority sectors in the Region?
3. What is the role of the different players in the region?
4. What are the region's needs?

The summary of the main contributions are shown in the table below:

Circular Economy	Priority Sectors	Role of the region's actors	Region's Needs
<p>Reflects the natural concept where "nothing is lost, everything is transformed";</p> <p>Contributes to Environmental, Economic and Social Sustainability;</p> <p>Reuse, repair, recycle and extend the life cycle of products and materials;</p> <p>Results in greater efficiency in the use and consumption of resources, less environmental impact and the generation of economic and social value.</p>	<p>Agri-food Agriculture</p> <p>Forestry Health Energy Textiles Transport Tourism</p> <p>↑ Environmental Impact; ↑ Opportunities to generate wealth, create jobs, implement CE strategies and create synergies and partnerships.</p>	<p>Adopting and promoting collaborative, conscious and transparent attitudes and cultures;</p> <p>Contributing to raising awareness among the general public about CE.</p>	<p>Awareness and Education;</p> <p>Community Involvement;</p> <p>Planning and Cooperation;</p> <p>Policies and Regulations;</p> <p>Innovation and Financing;</p> <p>Development and Implementation of Circular Economy Strategies (long way to go).</p>

On the following pages, the detailed conclusions are presented, endeavouring to describe as accurately as possible the contributions made by the participants during the participatory session. The original notes are archived and available on request (by e-mail to gic@ipc.pt).

1. What is Circular Economy?

As the Circular Economy (CE) is a concept that is generally perceived and interpreted differently by different people and entities, the reflection resulted in a set of contributions that allow us to see whether the group of participants understands the Circular Economy as a strategy that reflects the natural cycle, where 'nothing is lost, everything is transformed' and that contributes to Environmental, Economic and Social Sustainability.

The group also mentioned that the CE can be translated into reusing, repairing, recycling and increasing the lifespan of products and materials, promoting recirculation and combating rapid waste. Thus, CE results in greater efficiency in the use and consumption of resources, a reduction in environmental impact and the creation of economic and social value in a sustainable and inclusive way.

The contributions collected were organised into the following 4 categories:

- Circular Economy
- Environmental Sustainability
- Economic Sustainability
- Social Sustainability

Circular Economy

The group reflected that CE is based on:

- Inspiration from nature: The CE reflects the natural cycle, where 'nothing is lost, everything is transformed', equating to the laws of thermodynamics.
- Circularity of resources: This involves reusing, repairing, recycling and extending the lifespan of products and materials, promoting recirculation rather than disposal.
- Efficient management: Maximising the use of resources and energy, reducing waste throughout the life cycle of products.
- Promoting quality: Creating products that are more durable, modular and repairable, guaranteeing longer life cycles and greater efficiency.
- Ecodesign: Thinking about circularity right from product design, favouring modularity, ease of repair and replacement of parts.

Environmental Sustainability

For the group, CE promotes Environmental Sustainability through the following:

- Reducing environmental impact;
- Reducing and recycling waste;
- Increasing the life cycle of products;
- Local and seasonal consumption;
- Green mobility;
- More efficient production models;
- Lower consumption;
- Bioeconomy and sustainability: Replacing fossil resources with bio-based materials, reducing environmental impact and the depletion of finite resources.

Economic Sustainability

The group pointed out that CE can represent an opportunity to generate wealth and stimulate the economy, as it can leverage:

- Creation of local jobs: CE can foster the creation of new businesses and stimulate the regional economy;
- Innovation and new business opportunities: Encourage new business models and technological solutions, such as circular hubs and digital repair and sharing platforms;
- New economic paradigm: Creating a more self-sufficient and resilient economy, promoting de-globalisation and valuing local and regional practices;
- Waste and resource management: Valuing waste, transforming it into resources for new production cycles, such as fertilisers or secondary raw materials;
- Regional affirmation: Highlighting territories as examples of circularity, increasing their attractiveness for companies and investors.

Social Sustainability

On a social level, the group reflected on how CE can be of added importance, as it promotes a culture of partnerships, sharing and transparency, based on:

- Reusing and sharing: Promoting the reuse of materials and products through local networks and collaborative platforms.
- Rethinking behaviour: Encouraging the transition from a consumerist culture to one of sufficiency and repair.
- Education and literacy: Training citizens to understand and adopt circular practices.
- Sharing Culture: Rescuing ancient practices and collective knowledge, where reuse and circularity were already intrinsic.

2. What are the priority sectors in the region?

During the session, the group of participants identified 14 sectors in which they consider it would be relevant to develop or implement CE strategies in the Coimbra region. Of these 14 sectors, 8 were identified as priorities. Of these 8, it was pointed out that the Agri-food and Agriculture sectors would be top priorities.

The sectors are listed below, with the priority sectors identified in bold:

- **Agri-food**
- **Agriculture**
- **Forestry**
- **Health**
- **Energy**
- **Textiles**
- **Transport**
- **Tourism**
- Education
- Water and Waste Treatment
- Hotels and Restaurants
- 3rd Sector
- Industry
- Construction

These sectors were identified by the group as priorities because, as well as resulting in significantly negative environmental impacts (waste and high levels of consumption; CO₂ emissions and the generation of potentially hazardous waste), they represent opportunities for wealth generation, job creation, the implementation of CE strategies and the creation of synergies and partnerships.

The agri-food sector was pointed out as one of the most relevant for implementing circular economy strategies in the Coimbra Region given its socio-economic importance and direct impact on the environment. The group mentioned as possible strategies the

optimisation of natural resources, the reduction of food waste throughout the production chain, the adoption of regenerative practices, such as the use of organic waste for composting and bioenergy, and the strengthening of short production and consumption circuits.

Forestry was the second sector most emphasised by the group, as it is one of the region's economic and environmental pillars, playing a crucial role in mitigating climate change, preserving biodiversity and providing renewable resources such as wood and biomass. The group also mentioned its potential for circularity, emphasising the reuse of biomass to create value, namely in energy production, the development of bioproducts and the promotion of a more sustainable and efficient economy.

The group also pointed out that the education sector should play a transversal and relevant role, namely in raising awareness and training different actors to transform behaviours and perceptions, as well as to adopt circular practices in all sectors of the economy.

3. What is the role of the different players in the region?

Challenged to reflect on what roles and responsibilities the different actors in the region should play in developing and implementing CE strategies in the region, the group identified several areas for action. These action areas, organised into 4 categories, highlight the importance of bringing the concept, practices and policies closer to communities, companies and the public sector, clarifying what CE is and raising awareness of the need for everyone to be part of the processes.

In addition, the group feels that the different actors have different roles, assigning the responsibility for adopting circular production strategies to companies and the responsibility for regulation, legislation and inspection to the different levels of national and local power. Consumers, on the other hand, have a responsibility to make conscious choices based on the consumption of sustainably produced goods and services.

There are responsibilities that cut across all actors, such as adopting and promoting collaborative, conscious and transparent attitudes and cultures.

The categories and roles/responsibilities identified are as follows:

Cross-cutting responsibilities

- Promote strategies based on a culture of partnership, sharing, collaboration and transparency between sectors;
- Promote collaborative production practices (e.g. cooperatives) and encourage social innovation in line with CE;
- Create showcases of circularity, where good practices can be observed and replicated.

Consumer

- Keep informed about the production methods of the goods and services they consume;
- Demand a change in consumption habits and attitudes in order to create collective impact;

- Choose products with minimal environmental impact and produced based on CE principles, thus becoming a transforming agent of production through their consumption choices.

Industry and Private Sector

- Adopt transparent data-sharing practices;
- Adopt strategies for valorising and reusing by-products;
- Seek out and take inspiration from successful conservation models integrated into the local economy (e.g. Malcata Lynx, Castro Verde).

Public Sector (local, regional and national)

- Invest in awareness-raising and education campaigns for the Circular Economy for all audiences, which make the CE attractive and promote local consumption, the protection of biodiversity and the adoption of sustainable practices;
- Create negative reinforcements (e.g. penalties) and positive reinforcements (e.g. financial incentives and recognition), in a balanced way and capable of, on the one hand, encouraging and rewarding the consumption and production of goods and services based on CE strategies, but also penalising and making less attractive the production and consumption of those with negative environmental impacts;
- Create national regulations and transposing international regulations, to bring about the transition according to clear rules and standards.
- Establish licensing criteria and waste management plans;
- Combat planned obsolescence;
- Invest in knowledge transfer to companies and empower local communities.
- Setting an example by including CE criteria in tender specifications for the purchase of goods and services.

4. What are the region's needs?

Regarding the region's CE needs, the group feels that the road to developing and implementing CE strategies is still long, given the characteristics of the social and business fabrics. Furthermore, the lack of knowledge of these practices and their benefits emphasises the needs identified and presents barriers and resistance to the transition to CE in the Coimbra region.

The group believes that this transition needs an integrated approach that combines education, participation, policies and innovation, involving the different players in the region in the process.

The needs collected are essentially organised into 4 categories:

Education and Awareness

- Include the circular economy in school curricula;
- Promote circular economy literacy among all actors, involving topics such as the life cycle of products and the valorisation of local solutions;
- Create marketing strategies to make the consumption of circular economy products "cool";
- Use concepts that attract young consumers. For example: "long life cycle"; "cool"; "fashion"; or "genuine".
- Create perceived value in circular solutions.
- Combat the disconnection between concept and practice: Despite being an attractive term ("cute" and "sexy"), CE is often confused with waste management, and it is necessary to communicate that it goes beyond that;
- Financial barriers: The transition to CE entails costs that generate disagreement about who should assume them - consumers, companies or governments.

Community Involvement

- Stimulate community spirit and activate the community for greater involvement and interest in circular practices;
- Promote community commitment by raising awareness and participation in the planning, development and implementation of solutions;

- Raise awareness among different players to the economic, social and cultural benefits of the circular economy;
- Invest in initiatives that create figures such as 'Circularity Facilitators';
- Provide mechanisms that facilitate circular practices, such as the reuse of materials and by-products;
- Facilitate repair processes for textiles, household appliances and other products;
- Create Cooperation mechanisms;
- Promote the visibility of actors with CE practices;
- Strategic Coordination: Improve planning and organisation between leaders, partners and facilitators;
- Combat lack of infrastructure: Increase recycling centres, containers and circularity initiatives in many regions.
- Dominant linear models: Society and companies are still very accustomed to linear production and consumption paradigms.

Policies and Regulations

- Update regulations related to waste and by-products to facilitate the transition to CE;
- Create incentives and penalties;
- Penalise unsustainable new products;
- Reduce the size and number of packaging used;
- Increased enforcement.

Innovation and Financing

- Promote research and development (R&D) for innovative circular economy solutions;
- Shift the focus of production towards top quality products;
- Create funding mechanisms that promote the development and implementation of CE strategies.

Workshop Evaluation

The evaluation was based on the opinions gathered at the end of the workshop, and a satisfaction questionnaire sent via email to all attendees.

At the end of the session, the general opinion was that the session had been very positive and useful, as it had been possible to address very relevant issues using a methodology that was very suitable for the group. The participants felt that the objectives had been achieved, and most of them were keen to continue being part of the process and to attend the next session.

Regarding the satisfaction questionnaire, take-up was low at the time (10 February 2025), with only 5 responses.

The questionnaire - which can be found in the annexes - consisted of 12 quantitative and 3 qualitative questions. It sought to assess the level of involvement of the participants, the methodology chosen, its application and the effectiveness of the session.

In the quantitative questions, they were asked to rate their agreement with the statement from 1 to 5, with 1 being 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 being 'Strongly Agree'.

The results from the 15 questions are presented below:

1. I felt welcomed and comfortable.

2. My voice and opinions were important to the debate.

3. I cooperated with other stakeholders during the workshop.

4. I engaged in the workshop and its' objectives.

5. Information was clear and direct.

6. The subjects on hand were relevant.

7. I enjoyed the methodology used.

8. The methodology was adequate to groups' characteristics.

9. The methodology was adequate to the workshop goals.

10. I learned something new.

11. It motivated me to try something new in Circular Economy.

12. I would participate again.

13. Aspects that could be better.

- Having more people participating and contributing.
- -
- Nothing to register.
- Nothing to mention.
- NA.

14. The workshop's negative points.

- I think the methodology worked very well.
- -
- At the moment, nothing to register.
- Nothing to mention.
- NA.

15. Would you do something different? What would you do?

- In this methodology, I wouldn't change anything.
- -
- At the moment, nothing to register.
- N/A.
- NA.

Photographs

Photo 1: Public presentation of the project

Photo 2: World Café session

Photo 3: Taking notes on contributions from the topic 'What is Circular Economy?'

Photo 4: World Café Session – Presentation of Results

Annexes

Anex 1: Attendance sheet

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Comunidade Intermunicipal da Região de Coimbra

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*Declaro que consinto que os dados aqui fornecidos sejam tratados para efeitos de registo na presente ação e no sentido de que me sejam enviadas informações sobre assunto em causa.

DUT Driving Urban Transitions

Co-funded by the European Union

This project has been funded by Formas, FCT, LME and MUR under the Driving Urban Transitions Partnership, which has been co-funded by the European Union.

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UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA

Dia: 05/12/2024
Local: Auditório do DEM-FCTUC, Paço II da UC
Hora: 18h00

FOLHA DE PRESENCAS

Assunto: 1ª Reunião do CirLab da Região de Coimbra

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Co-funded by the European Union

This project has been funded by Formas, FCT, LME and MUR under the Driving Urban Transitions Partnership, which has been co-funded by the European Union.

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Annex 2 - Satisfaction Questionnaire, available at:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdfQaUtDu4hjDwJCqlihXqEDrOY351GfQNZjcNaw8eLQuKfrQ/viewform>

10. Aprendi algo novo. *

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

11. Fiquei motivado para tentar algo novo na Economia Circular. *

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

12. Voltaria a participar. *

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

13. Os aspetos que poderiam ser melhorados no workshop: *

A sua resposta

14. Os pontos negativos do workshop: *

A sua resposta

15. Faria algo diferente? O que é que faria? *

A sua resposta

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